

LEARNERS' ATTITUDE IN TEACHING AND LEARNING OF KISWAHILI IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS: CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES

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Abstract:

Existing studies indicate that increasing effectiveness in teaching and learning positively influence performance. However, challenges may diminish effectiveness in teaching and learning leading to poor performance. The study focused on challenges in relation to learners' attitude towards Kiswahili and the strategies for coping with the challenges in teaching of Kiswahili in public secondary schools in Hamisi Sub-county, Vihiga County, Kenya. Study population was 4,106 form four students, 139 Kiswahili teachers, 47 principals and 1 Quality Assurance and Standards Officer. Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) formula was used to select a sample of 351 form four students and purposive sampling was used to select 42 form four teachers of Kiswahili. Saturated sampling technique was used to select 42 principals and 1 QASO. In this study,

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questionnaires and interview schedule were used in data collection. Quantitative data was analysed by descriptive statistics involving frequencies, means and percentages and presented on tables. Qualitative data was categorized into themes and reported in verbatim excerpts. Learners had positive attitude towards objectives and content at mean ratings of 3.02 and 2.94 respectively. However, learners had challenges in teaching methods and evaluation techniques. They had negative attitude towards teaching methods and evaluation techniques at mean ratings of 2.44 and 2.34 respectively. The main strategy for coping with these challenges was speaking Kiswahili on specific days highly applied at 3.22. Motivational speeches and rewards as well as encouraging wide reading were lowly applied at 2.45 and 2.43 respectively. Other strategies that emerged from the study were use of Kiswahili clubs, discouraging learners from listening to adulterated Kiswahili and making Kiswahili lessons interesting. In conclusions, though the overall learners' attitude towards objectives and content is positive, they have negative attitude towards teaching methods and evaluation techniques. Schools have various strategies for coping with the challenges applied at different extents. The study recommends that schools endeavor to inculcate positive attitude among learners towards teaching methods and evaluation procedures by making them learner centered and properly guiding them in these activities. Teachers need to expose learners to a variety of teaching methods and evaluation techniques and provide timely feedback. This will make learners more enthusiastic and confident and in turn improve performance. The study findings may benefit teachers, scholars, curriculum developers, policy makers and other interested parties in understanding the challenges in relation to learners' attitude, adopting and strengthening the strategies as well as seeking solutions to the challenges in order to improve the teaching and learning process.

Keywords: learners' attitude, challenges, strategies

1. Introduction

Teaching is very important in curriculum implementation. If there are challenges in teaching, then learning is affected and good performance may not be realized. Increasing the effectiveness in teaching would have a large enduring impact on performance (Murphy & Machin, 2011). Teachers of Kiswahili and students may be faced with challenges relating to learners' attitude that make it difficult for them to realize good performance in national examinations. They may have to apply strategies to cope with these challenges.

Learners' attitude is very important in language teaching. It may determine if the learners get what the teacher teaches. Verma (2005) reports that attitude plays a role in language teaching and learning in India. The study was conducted among 350 students at different English medium universities. Students had negative attitude towards English which developed at secondary school level hence they were not putting any effort to learn at tertiary level. Students dropped courses due to lack of proficiency in

English. This report is similar to that of Ming, (2011) where poor attitude towards English was a factor contributing to poor performance in Malaysia. The study by Verma was conducted among tertiary level students while the current study was carried out among secondary school students. Ming on the other hand used questionnaires only while the current study used questionnaires and interview schedule. Though these studies are important in highlighting the challenges, they were done in different settings therefore the results could be generalized to the Kenyan context hence the need to carry a similar study in Kenya. Moreover all have been done in teaching and learning of English, hence there was need for a similar study in Kiswahili.

Elsewhere in Africa challenges relating to learners' attitude in teaching and learning particularly in English language have been reported. Sa'ad and Usman (2014) report that negative attitude was one of the major causes of poor performance in English in Nigeria. The study by Sa'ad and Usman relied questionnaires only for data collection while the current study used interview schedule in addition to the questionnaires. Also this study was in English language while the current study was in Kiswahili. In addition the study was done in different country Nigeria, therefore the results could not be generalized to the Kenyan context hence the need for the current study.

In Kenya, Mbiti (2013) cites poor attitude of students towards Kiswahili as a challenge facing teachers and students in the process of teaching and learning Kiswahili in public secondary schools. Kang'ahi, Indoshi, Okwach and Osodo (2012) observe that learners' attitude towards Kiswahili was positive but noted irony in that their performance was poor. Studies by Mose (2007) and Kobia and Ndiga (2013) found that students had negative attitude towards Kiswahili. However, these studies focused on Kiswahili as a subject in general whereas the current study focused on four elements of the Kiswahili curriculum. Opimbi (2011) did a study on attitude based on the elements of the Kiswahili curriculum and observed that students in Siaya District (currently Sub-county) had negative attitude towards content and teaching methods and positive attitude towards objectives and valuation techniques. The current study sought to find out if the same differences in attitude towards different elements of the curriculum applied among students in Hamisi Sub-county where the current research was carried out.

It is important to find out how schools were coping with the challenges in relation to learners' attitude in teaching of Kiswahili in secondary schools. Kanyi (2015) studied strategies for coping with challenges in English. There was need to do a similar study in Kiswahili focusing on strategies for coping with attitude related challenges. Most of the studies done in Kiswahili; challenges in implementation of the Kiswahili curriculum; Kobia (2009) and Malilo (2014), factors influencing implementation of the Kiswahili curriculum Opimbi (2011) and Karimi (2014) and causes of poor performance in Kiswahili Maina (2003) did not seek views of respondents on coping strategies. Researchers who have attempted to point out coping strategies have ignored the views of respondents which are important. They have ended up giving the strategies as their

recommendations. This leaves it to speculation as to whether there were attempts to apply the strategies and if so to what extent. This study sought to bridge this gap.

Kiswahili language is used widely for communication in East and Central Africa (Chimera, 1998). Despite the importance of Kiswahili, performance in national examinations has not been impressive. A case in point is Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE) examination performance of the year 2012 where the national mean score attained was 35.81%. This was a significant decline of 13.01% from the previous year 2011 (Ngirachu, 2013). Kiswahili is one of the subjects which the Minister of Education wanted probed due to poor performance. KNEC reports (KNEC, 2008; KNEC, 2010) point out that, students are unable to express themselves effectively in Kiswahili and directly lift answers from comprehension passages hence the answers lack flow. Furthermore, Momanyi (2009) reveals that secondary school graduates have low communicative competencies in Kiswahili. Even at the university, Kiswahili students exhibit weaknesses in the language. Kimemia (2001) observes that even Kiswahili students at the universities continue to show incompetence in speaking and writing.

Performance in Kiswahili in K.C.S.E examinations in Kenya has not been impressive. This has raised concern among stakeholders. During the release of 2012 KCSE results, the Minister of Education ordered a probe into the poor performance of Kiswahili. In the year 2012 the national mean score attained was 35.81% a significant decline of 13.01% from the year 2011. The performance in national examinations in Kiswahili in Hamisi Sub-County has remained poor. The KCSE examination average score was 5.43 out of the possible 12 points between the years 2010 and 2014. For these years, the sub-county showed the poorest trend in performance in Kiswahili in Vihiga County. Despite this poor performance, an assessment of challenges and strategies in relation to learners' attitude in teaching and learning of Kiswahili had not been done. Focusing on challenges and strategies can give insight on how to improve teaching and learning and in turn improve the performance of learners in Kiswahili.

The purpose of this study was to assess the challenges and strategies in relation to learners' attitude in teaching and learning of Kiswahili in public secondary schools in Hamisi Sub-county.

The objectives were:

- 1) To assess challenges in relation to learners' attitude in teaching and learning of Kiswahili in public secondary schools in Hamisi Sub-county.
- 2) To establish strategies for coping with the challenges in relation to learners' attitude in teaching and learning of Kiswahili in public secondary schools in Hamisi Sub-county.

2. Literature Review

Negative attitude towards Kiswahili in Kenya is historical. Glogowsky (2008) says that though the problem of lack of interest in reading language is found even in developed countries, in Kenya it is compounded by deep rooted issues that have been part of the

system since 1963. Language policies in the country have always promoted English which is a foreign language. Whitely (1974:484) cites a survey conducted among secondary school teachers where teachers drew to the problem of negative attitude towards Kiswahili. At that time, students were discouraged from using any other language outside the class other than English. Any Kenyan who did not speak English it meant that his/her formal education was not advanced beyond primary school level (Kennedy, 1984). A person was considered learned if he exhibited good mastery of English. Today the situation may not be different.

Despite Kiswahili being a national language since 1974, it is still taught as a subject and it has not reached a level where it could be used as a medium of instruction. Every government sponsored commission from colonial era to date has offered nothing short of hindrance to Kiswahili's triumph over English as a medium of instruction (Chimerah, 1998). Apart from English being taught as a subject it is also the sole medium of instruction. The Phelps-Stokes commission of 1924 emphasized training in tasks that require the use of hands while the Beecher commission totally ignored Kiswahili. The Binns' report of 1952 recommended that Kiswahili be eliminated except in areas where it was the mother tongue. English was endorsed as a medium of instruction in all grades by the Pretor/Hutasoit commission of late 1950s (Chimera, 1998). This was endorsed again with slight change of Kiswahili becoming a compulsory subject by the Kenya Education Commission of 1964. In the Gachathi commission of 1976, Kiswahili would be an important subject in primary and high school. Though this had been done, serious teaching and planning for Kiswahili was not addressed because the subject was not examinable.

It is the Mackay commission of 1981 that made Kiswahili a compulsory and examinable subject in all grades (Chimerah, 1998). With the continued emphasis in English, students therefore would give priority to English over Kiswahili. Glogowsky (2008) says when students and teachers speak of encouraging a culture of reading they invariably mean the culture of reading English. Students have also not appreciated the role of Kiswahili in career choice. Malilo (2014) noted that students do not see Kiswahili as an important subject in career prospects. Such students may not give the subject the attention it deserves.

Because of language policies that have continued to favor English over the years, parents also tended to encourage their children in English than in Kiswahili. Maina (2003) says that most parents feel that Kiswahili is not a very important subject compared to others like Sciences and Mathematics. They discourage their children from devoting a lot of time studying Kiswahili. Children's perception of their parents' support is related to their attitude towards a subject. Malilo (2014) notes that English has been given preference by most parents. Therefore parents might have played a role in developing the attitude the learners have towards Kiswahili.

Even where a learner has the skills he will not be able to use them in an autonomous way unless the underlying attitudes are there as well, (Tomlinson, 1998:296). To promote attitude alongside skills acquisition, the learner should be encouraged to reflect on what they are doing and why. Glogowsky (2008) says that

even when students speak in Kiswahili outside classroom, the Kiswahili spoken is riddled with grammatical errors. It is therefore important to establish if negative attitude of learners towards Kiswahili is a challenge in teaching and learning of the subject.

Studies on attitude have been carried out in Kiswahili Karimi (2014), studied factors influencing implementation of Kiswahili curriculum in public primary schools in Igoji Division Meru County. The study targeted Kiswahili teachers, head teachers and class eight pupils and used descriptive survey design. Data was collected by use of questionnaires and interview schedule. The study revealed that pupils had negative attitude towards Kiswahili. However, the study was carried at Primary school level while the current was carried at secondary school level.

A study by was carried out by Mose (2007) on factors affecting implementation of Kiswahili curriculum reforms in public secondary schools in Ngong Division of Kajiado district. Of the 224 form three students used in the study 69.5 % were found to have negative attitude towards Kiswahili as subject. A similar study was carried out by Kobia and Ndiga (2013) on the influence of secondary school students' attitude towards the implementation of Kiswahili curriculum in Igembe South District Meru County. The study employed descriptive survey research design. Target population was form four students. Data was collected using questionnaires. The results showed that the students had negative attitude towards Kiswahili as a subject. However the two studies focused on attitude of students towards Kiswahili as a subject in general while the current this researcher studied attitude of students towards Kiswahili curriculum involving the four elements namely objectives, content, teaching methods and evaluation procedures.

In a study by Opimbi (2011) on factors influencing implementation of Kiswahili curriculum attitude was one of the factors. The study was carried out in Siaya District. Attitude was measured based on the four elements of the curriculum namely objectives, teaching methods, content and evaluation. Results from the study showed that students had positive attitude towards objectives and evaluation techniques and negative attitude towards content and teaching methods. The current study sought to find out if the same differences in attitude towards different elements of the curriculum applied among students in Hamisi Sub-county where the current research was carried out. Another study was done by Mbito (2013) studying challenges facing teachers and students in the process of teaching and learning Kiswahili in public secondary schools in Kiambu District. The study involved form four students Kiswahili teachers, principals, Heads of Departments and QASO. Data was collected using questionnaires and interview schedule. From the study, poor attitude of students towards Kiswahili was a challenge facing teachers and students in the process of teaching and learning Kiswahili.

Kang'ahi et al (2012) carried out a study on teaching styles and learners' achievement in Kiswahili language in secondary schools. The study was conducted form four students and teachers of Kiswahili. The study indicated that learners' attitude towards Kiswahili was positive but noted irony in that their performance was poor. In the studies by Mbito (2013) and Kang'ahi at el (2012), measurement of learners' attitude

towards Kiswahili was not based on the four elements of the curriculum objectives, teaching methods, content and evaluation like the current study. Moreover when learners are performing poorly in a subject it is important to gauge their attitude towards that subject. This was the case in the current study.

Despite the challenges teaching and learning has to take place. Therefore strategies for coping with the challenges in relation to attitude in teaching and learning Kiswahili have to be applied. Learners' positive attitude in Kiswahili can be cultivated by use of motivational speeches and rewards. Harrison (2004) observes that teachers' enthusiasm and encouragement are the greatest gifts they can give the students they teach. In addition Maina (2003) observes that motivation is crucial force which determines whether learners embark on a task at all, how much they devote to it and how long they can persevere. Without encouragement resources and knowledge may be potentially fruitless. The new constitution passed in 2010 made Kiswahili official language alongside English. Schools are better placed to ensure that citizens embrace Kiswahili as official language. Teachers have a role to play in ensuring that this noble achievement is made a reality. Motivational speeches and rewards can influence students to embrace Kiswahili not only as a subject but also as national and official language in Kenya. Mbiti (2013) sought views of respondents on solutions to learners' negative attitude. In the study, respondents recommended rewarding as a way of addressing the challenge of poor attitude and improving performance. However it was not clear if the strategy was being applied or not. This study sought to assess the extent to which motivational speeches and rewards as a strategy was being applied to cope with the challenge.

Another strategy is cultivation of reading culture in Kiswahili. Glogowsky (2008) emphasizes the need to cultivate reading culture in Kiswahili. This goes along with provision of adequate reading materials. Gathumbi and Masembe (2005) explain three purposes of reading; for survival, for learning and for pleasure. Students need to be encouraged to read for pleasure. There is need for students to be encouraged to read more books apart from the ones prescribed in school. Failure to use supplementary books contributes to poor reading culture hence learners lack interest in the subject.

Schools encourage speaking of particular languages on particular days in what is referred to as language policy. These policies differ from one school to another. In most schools language policies involve English and Kiswahili where specific days are set aside for speaking English and others for Kiswahili. However, many schools have language policies that tend to favor English at the expense of Kiswahili mainly because English is the language of instruction. By using Kiswahili on specific days, the learners to build on their proficiency and increase their confidence in the language. The study by Mbiti (2013) gave language policy as a possible solution to the challenge of negative attitude. If the respondents already knew that this strategy would work then there was need to find out if they were already applying it hence this study

Most of the studies done on challenges in implementation of the Kiswahili curriculum; Kobia, (2009), Malilo, (2014), factors influencing implementation of the Kiswahili curriculum Opimbi (2011), causes of poor performance in Kiswahili Maina

(2003) did not seek views of respondents on strategies for coping with the challenges. Researchers who have attempted to give coping strategies give them as their recommendations. This ignores the input of respondents on the coping strategies. This study sought to bridge this gap.

3. Research Methodology

The study used descriptive survey design. The purpose of descriptive survey is description of state of affairs as it exists (Kombo & Tromp, 2006:71). The design has the ability to yield a great deal of accurate information. Gall and Borg (1996) state that survey research is a systematic way of collecting data by obtaining opinions and answers from selected respondents who represent the population of interest. The design enabled the researcher to systematically obtain and analyse data by surveying a sample of the population.

The study was carried out in Hamisi Sub-County in Vihiga County Kenya. It is one of the four sub-counties of Vihiga County. It was carved out of the larger Vihiga County, formerly referred to as Vihiga District in 2007. The area was selected for the study because it had the lowest KCSE Kiswahili mean scores in the county for the years 2010-2014. The average mean score for those years was 5.43 out of the possible 12.00 points.

The sub-county had 47 public secondary schools where the study was carried out. The study population was 4,106 form four students, 139 teachers of Kiswahili, 47 principals and 1 QASO. A sample of 351 students was drawn using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size estimate table. A sample of 42 form four teachers of Kiswahili was drawn through purposive sampling technique. This sample represented 30% of the total population. Babbie (1998) points out that 30% of any homogenous group gives a scientific representation of the population under study. Saturated sampling technique was used to select 42 principals and 1 QASO. Saturated sampling is a non probability procedure in which all the members of the target population are selected (Gall & Borg, 1996).

Face and content validity were tested by subjecting the questionnaires and interview schedules to three experts of Maseno University. Two experts were from Department of Educational Communication, Technology and Curriculum Studies and one expert was from Department of Kiswahili and other African Languages. The experts scrutinized the instruments questions in each of the sub-sections and judged their relevance to the objectives of the study. A pilot study was also carried out to ascertain content validity and reliability. The feedback obtained from the pilot study and suggestions and recommendations from the experts were used to improve the efficacy of the data collection instruments. The researcher strictly adhered to professional ethics while conducting the research. To do so the researcher observed the right of voluntary consent, confidentiality, anonymity of respondents and necessity of data protection.

Data for analysis in this study was yielded from questionnaires of students and teachers and interview of principals and QASO. The data was coded and organized for analysis. Items on teacher and student questionnaires on challenges and strategies in teaching of Kiswahili were scored on rating scales.

Attitude of learners was measured on a scale of 4 points: SD-Strongly Disagree = 1 point, D-Disagree =2 points, A-Agree = 3 points and SA-Strongly Agree = 4 points. The interpretation is shown in the Table 1.

Table 1: Interpretation of Challenges in relation to Learners' Attitude

No.	Range of mean score	Interpretation
1.	1.00 - 2.49	Negative attitude
2.	2.50 – 4.00	Positive attitude

Items on strategies were scored on a scale of 4 points: NA-Not Applied = 1 point, FA-Fairly Applied = 2 points, OA-Often Applied = 3 points and AA-Always Applied=4 points. The interpretation is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Interpretation of Strategies for Coping with the Challenges

No.	Range of mean score	Interpretation
1.	1.00 - 2.49	Lowly applied
2.	2.50 – 4.00	Highly applied

Quantitative data yielded was analyzed using descriptive statistical methods including frequencies, percentages and means and presented in tables. Mugenda and Mugenda (2003), note that descriptive statistics enables the researcher to describe a distribution of scores or measurements using a few indices or statistics. Qualitative data yielded in form of comments and suggestions from open ended questions on the students and teachers questionnaires and the interview of principals and QASO was categorized into selected themes. Thematic analysis was done where major concepts or themes were identified and reported in form of verbatim excerpts.

4. Results and Discussion

This section presents findings of the research. This study sought to assess the challenges and strategies in relation to learners' attitude in teaching and learning of Kiswahili.

4.1 Challenges in Teaching and Learning of Kiswahili in Relation to Learners' Attitude

The study sought views on learners' attitude towards Kiswahili in relation to objectives, content, teaching methods and evaluation.

a. Attitude towards Objectives

Respondents were provided with a list of statements about objectives and required to choose by ticking appropriately on the scale below: 1=Strongly Disagree 2= Disagree 3=Agree 4=Strongly Agree. Data was analyzed as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Students' Responses on their Attitude towards Objectives of Teaching and Learning Kiswahili (n=351)

Statement	SD		D		A		SA		M.S
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
1. By learning Kiswahili I have further developed the concepts I learned in primary school.	0	0	0	0	145	41.3	206	58.7	3.58
2. I am happy with the reading, writing, speaking and listening skills developed in Kiswahili.	0	0	0	0	153	43.6	198	56.4	3.56
3. By learning Kiswahili I think creatively and critically and can express myself clearly.	37	10.5	150	42.7	133	37.9	31	8.8	2.45
4. I do not like using Kiswahili for everyday communication.	108	30.8	70	19.9	75	21.4	98	27.9	2.47
5. I identify and value the various aspects of Kiswahili language and literature.	70	19.9	139	39.6	100	28.5	42	12.0	2.32
6. By learning Kiswahili I take interest in emerging issues in the society.	20	5.7	22	6.3	211	60.1	98	27.9	3.10
7. By learning Kiswahili I appreciate various cultural aspects.	19	5.4	50	14.3	192	54.7	90	25.6	3.00
8. By learning Kiswahili I can conserve the environment for sustainable development.	17	4.8	23	6.6	127	36.8	184	52.4	3.36
9. I enjoy reading and becoming better in Kiswahili.	10	2.9	19	5.4	165	47.0	157	44.7	3.33
10. I do not like Kiswahili as national language.	40	11.3	52	14.8	97	27.6	162	46.1	3.08
Overall Mean									3.02

Key: SD = Strongly Disagree; D = Disagree; A = Agree; SA = Strongly Agree; F = Frequency.

As shown on Table 3, students indicated overall positive attitude towards objectives of Kiswahili curriculum at a mean rating of 3.02. This was corroborated by the teachers. On their opinion about learners' attitude towards objectives, 35(83.3%) teachers felt that the attitude was positive while 7(16.7%) felt it was negative. However, students indicated negative attitude to objectives 8, 9 and 10 with mean ratings of 2.45, 2.47 and 2.32 respectively. To statement 3; students think creatively and critically and can express themselves clearly in Kiswahili 37(10.5%) strongly disagreed, 150(42.7%) disagreed, 133(37.9%) agreed and 31(8.8%) strongly agreed. To statement 4; students do not like using Kiswahili in their everyday communication, 98(27.9%) strongly disagreed, 75(21.4%) disagreed, 70(19.9%) agreed and 108(30.8%) strongly agreed. To statement 5; students identify and value aspects of Kiswahili language and literature 70(19.9%) strongly disagreed, 139(39.6%) disagreed, 100(28.5%) agreed and 42(12.0%) strongly agreed.

Negative attitude of students to objectives 3, 4 and 5 which are largely on speaking skill as indicated by the students could be attributed failure of the teaching and learning process to adequately develop this skill. Glogowsky (2008) says that the Kiswahili spoken by students outside the classroom is riddled with grammatical errors. Also in an education system that does not directly evaluate oral communication competence among learners practice in such communication may be ignored hence not achieving the objectives. Momanyi (2009) revealed secondary school graduates had low communicative competence in Kiswahili. Teachers tend to give more emphasis to skills that are directly tested in national examinations. Kupur (2008) asserts that language assessment should give an opportunity to students to demonstrate what they know and what they can do with the language. Similarly, Nkechi (2008) faults examinations that do not test the communicative skills necessary for performing real life tasks. In such a situation language learning is restricted to the classroom.

b. Attitude towards Content

Respondents were provided with a list of statements about content and were required to choose by ticking appropriately on the scale below: 1=Strongly Disagree 2= Disagree 3=Agree 4=Strongly Agree. Data was analyzed as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Students' Responses on their Attitude towards Content
in Teaching and Learning Kiswahili (n=351)

Statement	SD		D		A		SA		M.S
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
1. I enjoy learning Kiswahili grammar.	7	4.8	30	8.5	174	49.6	130	37.0	3.18
2. Social linguistics is boring.	27	7.7	55	15.7	104	29.6	165	47.0	3.15
3. I like learning oral literature.	55	15.7	141	40.2	101	28.7	54	15.3	2.43
4. I have a good feeling towards literature.	16	4.6	33	9.4	100	28.5	202	57.5	3.39
5. I do not like poetry.	14	4.0	25	7.1	114	32.5	198	56.4	3.41
6. I enjoy learning compositions.	44	12.5	193	55.0	75	21.4	39	11.1	2.13
Overall Mean									2.94

Key: SD = Strongly Disagree; D = Disagree; A = Agree; SA = Strongly Agree; F = Frequency.

From Table 4, students indicated that they had positive attitude towards content at mean rating of 2.94. Teachers also had a similar view that their students' attitude towards content in general was positive. On their opinion about learners' attitude towards content, 31(73.8%) teachers viewed the attitude as positive while 11(26.2%) viewed it as negative. As indicated by the students, positive attitude was evident grammar, social linguistics, literature and poetry. However, students had negative attitude towards compositions and oral literature at a mean rating of 2.13 and 2.43 respectively. On statement 3 that students like learning about oral literature 55(15.7%) strongly disagreed, 141(40.2%) disagreed, 101(28.7%) agreed and 54(15.3%) strongly agreed while on statement 6 students enjoy learning compositions 44(12.5%) of students strongly disagreed, 193(55.0%) disagreed, 75(21.4%) agreed and 39(11.1%) strongly agreed.

Negative attitude towards oral literature and compositions was probably because of wide scope. Opimbi (2011) reported that attitude of learners towards content in general was positive yet reported that the content was too wide. Negative attitude towards these two areas could also imply that students are not motivated to handle this content areas hence may not perform well. There is need to cultivate positive attitude towards these content areas.

c. Attitude towards Teaching Methods

Respondents were provided with a list of statements about teaching methods and were required to choose by ticking appropriately on the scale below: 1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Agree 4=Strongly Agree. Data was analyzed.

Table 5: Students' Responses on their Attitude towards Teaching Methods in Teaching and Learning Kiswahili (n=351)

Statement	SD		D		A		SA		M.S
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
1. I understand better when I discover Kiswahili concepts on my own.	76	21.7	170	48.4	74	21.1	31	8.8	2.17
2. I understand well when Kiswahili concepts are dramatized.	20	5.7	35	10.0	100	28.5	196	55.8	3.34
3. I like learning through language games	86	24.5	107	34.5	88	25.0	70	19.9	2.40
4. I understand better when I learn with my peers in a group.	80	22.8	163	46.4	69	19.7	39	11.1	2.19
5. I like it when I learn through debates.	71	20.2	83	23.6	104	29.6	93	26.5	2.62
6. I understand well when the teacher lectures.	171	48.7	149	42.5	21	6.0	10	2.8	1.62
7. I like learning Kiswahili through radio and video.	40	11.3	64	18.2	176	50.1	71	20.2	2.79
Overall mean score									2.44

Key: SD = Strongly Disagree; D = Disagree; A = Agree; SA = Strongly Agree; F = Frequency.

From Table 5, overall attitude towards teaching methods was negative at 2.44. Students indicated positive attitude of towards, dramatization at 3.34, radio and video at 2.79, debates at 2.62. Positive attitude towards these methods could be because they are learner centered and interesting.

Students had negative attitude towards most of the teaching methods; lectures 1.62, discovery at 2.17, group work 2.19 and language games at 2.40. Students did not like lectures probably because they are not learner centered and monotony of the method. Ambuko (2008) observed that lecturing was the most popular method of teaching among teachers. The study by Ambuko further advocated for other teaching methods to help cater for all students. Learners' dislike for discovery, group work and language games which are learner centered could be due to lack of proper guidance from teachers on how to go about these activities, lack of exposure to such activities and inadequate time. Yuanina (2010) observes that approaches that involve a lot of time but involve learners such as dramatization and discovery were rarely used. Teevno (2010) researching on challenges of teaching English in secondary schools noted that

development of the four language skills was poor as teachers rarely used teaching methods such as group work. Discovery and language games also require thinking creatively which the learners were not good at as observed in the objectives. Negative attitude towards these methods may also imply that the students did not like working on their own.

Majority of teachers however thought that the attitude of learners towards teaching methods was positive. From the opinion of teachers, 27(64.3%) of them perceived attitude as positive while 15(35.7) perceived it as negative. The difference in opinion between the teachers and students on teaching methods could imply that the teachers did not understand their learners well. Still it could also mean that teachers did not tailor their teaching methods to the needs of learners. Though teachers knew the teaching methods that their learners liked, they did not regularly use them. Petty (2009) asserts that discovering and meeting learners needs increases their chances of success. Reyneke et al (2010) noted that though teachers felt well equipped to cope with the curriculum, practical implementation remained a challenge. Reyneke et al (2010) further noted that only 39.75% of teachers indicated they involve their learners in classroom activities. Teachers therefore need to discover and meet learners' needs in their teaching methods. They need to tailor their teaching methods to the needs of the learners.

d. Attitude towards Evaluation Techniques

Respondents were provided with a list of statements on evaluation techniques and were required to choose by ticking appropriately on the scale below: 1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Agree 4=Strongly Agree. Data was analyzed as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Students' Responses on their Attitude towards Evaluation Techniques in Teaching and Learning Kiswahili (n=351)

Statement	SD		D		A		SA		M.S
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
1. Am comfortable with reading and answering questions from passages.	149	42.4	101	28.7	61	17.3	40	11.3	3.02
2. I do like oral presentation exercises.	172	49.0	137	39.0	28	8.0	16	4.0	1.69
3. I do not enjoy writing summaries from passages in Kiswahili.	90	25.6	163	46.4	67	19.1	31	8.8	2.11
4. I like writing compositions and essays in Kiswahili.	79	22.5	156	44.5	72	20.5	44	12.5	2.23
5. I like question-answer exercises.	30	8.5	50	14.3	141	40.2	130	37.0	3.05
6. I have a good feeling towards Kiswahili dictation exercises.	110	31.3	191	54.4	31	8.8	19	5.4	1.88
7. I enjoy doing punctuation exercises.	100	28.4	181	51.5	46	13.1	24	6.8	1.98
8. I like gap filling exercises.	91	25.9	179	51.0	70	19.9	11	3.1	2.00
9. I do not like listening comprehension exercises.	32	9.1	61	17.3	92	26.2	166	47.2	3.11
Overall mean score									2.34

Key: SD = Strongly Disagree; D = Disagree; A = Agree; SA = Strongly Agree; F = Frequency.

From Table 6, students had negative attitude towards evaluation techniques in Kiswahili at a mean rating of 2.34. The teachers also had a similar view that in general students had negative attitude towards evaluation techniques. From the teachers' opinions 26 (61.9%) perceived the students attitude as negative while 16(38.1%) perceived it as positive. From the students responses, negative attitude was evident in most of the evaluation techniques; oral presentations 1.69, writing summaries from passages 2.11, writing compositions and essays 2.23, dictation 1.88, punctuation 1.98 and gap filling exercises 2.00 These findings could be because the teachers may not have made the evaluation techniques learner friendly. There could also be delay by teachers in providing feedback to learners. Mbitio (2013) reports that teachers rarely marked learners' home work in Kiswahili. Teachers may also not be evaluating students regularly. KIE (2010) found that most teachers tested their learners once a week. This evaluation is inadequate especially for a language and a compulsory subject like Kiswahili.

The teachers may have also made the evaluation techniques examination oriented. The demand for students to pass examinations mean teachers concentrate on test taking skills used in final examinations hence they may not work to cultivating positive attitude towards evaluation among learners. Kobia (2009) observed tendency of teachers to concentrate on skills that are directly examined at national examinations and ignoring those that are not. For instance dictation and oral presentation which are not used in examinations were the most unpopular among the students at the rating of 1.88 and 1.69 respectively. On whether students like oral presentations 172(49.0%) strongly disagreed, 137 (39.0%) disagreed, 28(8.0%) agreed and 16(4.0%) strongly agreed. A study by Maina (2003) indicated that teachers rarely used oral presentations. This means that evaluation techniques that are not likely to be used in the final examinations were rarely used. This could imply that evaluation techniques applied were not appropriately evaluating what was learnt. Teachers need to apply evaluating techniques that aid in acquisition of language skills.

Students indicated they had positive attitude towards reading and answering questions from passages 3.02, question-answer exercises 3.05 and listening comprehension exercises 3.11. Reasons for students liking of these evaluation techniques could be because answers are provided in the passages and listening comprehensions. It could point to students' liking for easy evaluation techniques. For the question answer technique, the teacher selects student s to answer the questions so not all the students may be required to answer. Table 7 shows a summary of results on learners' attitude towards Kiswahili.

4.2 Summary of the Results on Attitude

The results on attitude of learners towards Kiswahili were summarized as follows:

Table 7: Summary of the Results on Attitude

Curriculum element	Mean score
1. Objectives	3.02
2. Content	2.94
3. Teaching methods	2.44
4. Evaluation techniques	2.34
Overall mean score	2.68

From Table 7, the general attitude of learners towards Kiswahili curriculum was positive with an overall mean rating of 2.68. However, students indicated positive attitude towards two elements of the curriculum namely objectives with a rating of 3.03 and content with a rating of 2.94 and negative attitude towards the other two elements teaching and learning methods with a rating of 2.44 and evaluation techniques with a rating of 2.68. Kang'ahi et al (2012) found that learners' attitude towards Kiswahili was positive. However, Kang'ahi noted irony in this perspective in that students had positive attitude yet the performance remained low. This study may explain the irony because it looked at the four elements of the curriculum hence observing that there was negative attitude in two elements teaching and methods and evaluation techniques while the study by Kang'ahi looked at the Kiswahili subject in general. Opimbi (2011) observed that students had negative attitude towards content and teaching methods while positive attitude was observed in objectives and evaluation. This presents a difference in outcome of these two studies on attitude towards content and evaluation techniques. The outcome of this study also differs from Mbito (2013) who found that attitude of students towards Kiswahili was negative. The differences in outcome may imply that attitude of learners was dependent on specific situations which were not part of this research.

In general the attitude of learners towards Kiswahili was viewed as positive. From the interviews, majority of the principals said they thought that learners' attitude towards Kiswahili curriculum in general was positive. The following are some of their remarks;

"I think the attitude is positive because during my interaction the teachers and learners the issue of negative attitude of students towards Kiswahili rarely arises." (Principal 12)

"I think the attitude of learners towards Kiswahili in general is positive. However, we cannot rule out negative among individual students. We need to keep encouraging our learners in the subject." (Principal 40)

"We have no major issue with attitude in Kiswahili; our problem is in the sciences and Mathematics." (Principal 17)

QASO: I think learners' attitude towards Kiswahili is does not pose a major challenge. I think the strategies in place in our schools have minimized the challenge.

However the general view that learners' attitude towards Kiswahili was positive may mean the subject was not being given more emphasis hence ending up with poor results. It could also point to the feeling that there were subjects that were worse off than Kiswahili as it emerged from the interviews. In this situation, the other subjects perceived to have a more serious challenge in learners' attitude would therefore be receiving more attention than Kiswahili. The results could also imply that the respondents lacked full information as far as attitude of students towards Kiswahili curriculum was concerned hence trusting the strategies that were in place for cultivation of positive attitude towards Kiswahili. It should also be appreciated that the teachers and principals views on learners' attitude may have been purely based on perception as they may not have measured it.

4.3 Strategies for Coping with Challenge of Negative Attitude of Learners

Respondents' views on strategies for coping with challenge of negative attitude of learners towards Kiswahili were sought. Teachers and students were asked to tick appropriately the extent to which listed strategies were applied in coping with negative attitude of learners towards Kiswahili curriculum using the scale of, 1=Not applied 2= Fairly applied 3=Often applied and 4=Always Applied. Results are as shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Teachers' (n=42) and Students' (n=351) Responses
 on Strategies for Coping with Challenge of Negative Attitude of Learners

Strategy		NA		FA		OA		AA		Mean Score	Overall M.S
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
1. Motivational speeches and rewards.	T	0	0	28	66.6	10	23.8	4	9.5	2.42	
	S	0	0	188	53.5	107	30.4	40	11.3	2.44	2.43
2. Encouraging wide reading.	T	0	0	26	61.9	11	26.2	5	11.9	2.50	
	S	0	0	192	54.7	89	25.3	70	19.9	2.40	2.45
3. Speaking Kiswahili on specific days (language policy).	T	0	0	7	16.6	15	35.7	20	47.6	3.30	
	S	0	0	81	22.7	135	38.4	135	38.4	3.15	3.22
Overall M.S										2.70	2.70

KEY: NA = Not Applied; FA = Fairly Applied; OA = Often Applied F = Frequency T = Teachers; S = Students.

Both teachers and students indicated that the listed strategies were all highly applied at a mean rating of 2.70. Speaking Kiswahili on specific days was the most popular strategy highly applied at a mean rating of 3.22. Also principals interviewed reported that the strategy was used in their schools to cope with the challenge.

"We have language policy in place. We speak in Kiswahili on Fridays, Saturdays and Sundays. During this time the learners can make maximum interaction in the language which is good for their attitude." (Principal 12)

"We have set aside days for learners to speak purely in Kiswahili. When we introduced the policy it was not easy but now I see them looking forward to the days set aside for Kiswahili. (Principal 34)

The overreliance on this strategy and failure to fully embrace the other strategies could imply that principals, teachers and students may not have understood this challenge hence concentrating on the speaking and listening skills in development of attitude and leaving out reading and writing skills.

Encouraging wide reading was lowly applied at a mean rating of 2.45. The low rating could be due to inadequate reading materials such as books newspapers and magazines as seen in another part of the research. This could be because students may prefer to read more in English. Malilo (2014) notes poor reading in Kiswahili with students preferring to read more of English which is a not only a compulsory subject but also the medium of instruction. Some of the teachers and students also may not have associated the strategy of wide reading with cultivation of positive attitude of learners towards Kiswahili. According to Gathumbi and Masembe (2005) wide reading can arouse interest in a language. In an education system that places a lot of importance in passing of examinations, students are encouraged to read for examinations. Students need to be encouraged read for the skill, knowledge and pleasure.

Motivational speeches and rewards were lowly applied at a mean rating of 2.43. To the teachers it was lowly applied at 2.42 while for the students it was lowly applied at 2.44. This could imply that the respondents have not associated this strategy with cultivation of positive attitude of learners towards Kiswahili. Mbito (2013) observed that 75% of schools did not have elaborate system of rewarding students in Kiswahili. Harrison (2004) observes that teachers' encouragement and enthusiasm is very important in teaching and learning process. Maina (2003) stresses the importance of motivation as a crucial force which determines whether learners embark on a task at all, how much they devote their time on it and how long they can persevere. It motivates the learner and arouses in the learner interest in the subject.

Other strategies emerged from the open ended questions of the questionnaires. A number of teachers and students revealed they had Kiswahili clubs where students got more exposed to the subject hence building their interest in it.

"Our Kiswahili clubs are useful in helping us to develop positive attitude in the subject. They engage in more language learning activities that may possible in normal forty minutes lesson." (Student 185)

"Clubs give learners an opportunity to interact more with the language and cultivate positive attitude. The clubs expose them to students of other schools where they get to interact and learn more." (Teacher 30)

Kiswahili clubs have activities that help develop the four language skills of speaking, listening, reading and writing which can help them cultivate positive attitude

towards the subject. This implies that learners have more opportunities to interact and learn from their peers. Therefore the clubs can be strengthened as a useful strategy in coping with challenges in relation to attitude.

Some teachers indicated they discouraged learners from watching and listening to programmes in the media which used adulterated Kiswahili. Some students had similar observations.

"We are discouraged from listening to radio stations which do not use Kiswahili correctly. This is because such stations can have a lot of influence on learners in terms of language development." (Student 47)

"Some media outlets do not use proper Kiswahili. It is good to advise students to keep off such outlets as they may mislead them." (Teacher 19)

Currently there seems to be no clear language policy in the media. Speakers use Kiswahili that is laden with grammatical errors. This greatly erodes the gains made in Kiswahili as the errors are transferred to the classroom and it becomes difficult for teachers to correct. Language is basically interactive. Gathumbi and Masembe (2005) observe that the ability to use language for interactive purposes is rarely taught in formal learning situations. It requires opportunities that allow language use in an interactive manner.

Some teachers said they try as much to make Kiswahili lessons more interesting to learners. They use this as a strategy of cultivating positive attitude towards Kiswahili among learners. Some of their remarks were as follows;

"I make my lessons as interesting as possible by involving the learners so that they own the subject." (Teacher 10)

"If you bore your students when teaching they tend to develop negative attitude towards the subject. To avoid this I make my lessons as lively as possible." (Teacher 26)

This means that teachers arouse the interest of learners in teaching and learning of Kiswahili as a way of cultivating positive attitude towards Kiswahili. Farrant (2006) points out the need to arouse interest of learners in teaching and learning of language. When teaching is interesting learners enjoy learning and look forward to having lessons in the subject. This helps develop in learners a liking for the subject.

5. Conclusions and Implications

5.1 Conclusions

Though the overall attitude of students towards Kiswahili is positive, students have negative attitude towards two elements of Kiswahili curriculum; teaching methods and evaluation techniques. Negative attitude towards teaching methods could be due to

lack of proper guidance from teachers on how to go about these activities, lack of exposure to such activities, inadequate resources and inadequate time. Learners' negative attitude towards evaluation techniques may be because teachers have not made them learner friendly, failure to evaluate learners regularly and delays in giving feedback to the learners. Teachers may also have made evaluation techniques examination oriented hence delinking evaluation from normal teaching and learning process.

Negative attitude towards Kiswahili is coped with by use of Speaking Kiswahili on specific days, encouraging wide reading and motivational speeches and rewards. Other strategies are; use of Kiswahili clubs, discouraging students from listening to adulterated Kiswahili and making Kiswahili lessons interesting.

5.2 Implications

From the study, the overall attitude of students towards Kiswahili was positive, however students had negative attitude towards two elements of Kiswahili curriculum; teaching methods and evaluation techniques. There is need therefore to inculcate positive attitude among learners towards teaching methods and evaluation procedures by making them learner centered and properly guiding them in these activities. Teachers need to expose learners to a variety of teaching methods and evaluation techniques and provide timely feedback. This will make learners more enthusiastic and confident and in turn improve performance. The study findings show that there were strategies for coping with the challenges applied at different extents. The coping strategies need to be strengthened. Solutions to the challenges in teaching and learning of Kiswahili in relation to learners' attitude can also be sought.

6. Recommendations

Schools should endeavor to inculcate positive attitude among learners towards teaching methods and evaluation procedures by making them learner centered and properly guiding them in these activities. Teachers need to expose learners to a variety of teaching methods and evaluation techniques and provide timely feedback. This will make learners more enthusiastic and confident and in turn improve performance.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest among the authors of this study.

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